

Analysing Literary Variants and Versioning: (How) Can LLMs Help?

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Use case: Goethe's lyric poems

- complex textual history
 - 3000+ texts (1755–1832)
 - 2500 mss, +300 prints
 - multiple versions
 - abundance of variants
- visualisation, → analysis

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Agenda

1. Emergence of a potential research field
2. Toward a theory of variation?
3. Which way forward in the digital / AI age?
4. Experiments

1. Emergence of a research field

Variation in F.G. Klopstock's *Messias*: Publication history

Relevant here:

- 1751: Cantos I–V
- 1755, vol. 1: Cantos I–V (revised), vol. 2: Cantos VI–X (new)
- 1756: reprint of vol. 2

Variation in F.G. Klopstock's *Messias*: G.E. Lessing's discovery

- 1751: Cantos I–V
- 1755, vol. 1: Cantos I–V (**revised**), vol. 2: Cantos VI–X (added)

About vol. 1 of 1755 edition: “the cantos themselves have been **altered and improved** in an extraordinary number of places.”

Lessing: Letters on the Most Recent Literature, 19th letter (1759)

Why bother with variants?

Lessing's approach

“Alterations and improvements [NB] that a poet like Klopstock makes to his works deserve not merely to be noted, but to be studied with the utmost diligence. In them one studies the finest **rules of art**; for what the masters of the art deem worth observing, those are rules.”

Lessing: Letters on the Most Recent Literature, 19th letter (1759)

single variants

→

underlying *règles de l'art*

subsumption

inference

What changes in *Messias*?

Lessing's analysis

- metrical changes
- changes in phrasing
 - in particular: dissolution of participial constructions
- changes in expression
- expansions
- additions
- omissions

confined to authorial and substantive variants (accidentals ignored)

What changes in *Messias*?

From individual variants to general patterns

“On all sides one finds examples of more definite metre, of purer phrasing, and of the choice of nobler expression. With regard to phrasing, he has, among other things, resolved a great number of participles wherever they made the periods too cumbersome or too obscure.

[Examples]

And so in a hundred other places.”

Lessing: Letters on the Most Recent Literature, 19th letter (1759)

From variants to aesthetics

Goethe's claim about C.M. Wieland's works

“[...] it is no exaggeration to say that a judicious and diligent man of letters, by comparing all the editions of our *Wieland* [...] could, from the gradual corrections of this author who labored tirelessly toward improvement [NB], derive the entire aesthetics.”

Goethe: Literarischer Sansculottismus (1795)

single variants → aesthetics (‘Geschmackslehre’)
inference

2. Toward a theory of variation?

Jan Mukařovský: *Varianty a stylistika* (1930)

German translation in *Poetica* 1968

- Example as starting point / basis: Jaroslav Vrchlický's *Z hlubin*
- challenges the normative view (later = improved versions → Lessing, Goethe: **absolute** aesthetic rules)
- early versions: more vivid and striking, everyday language; later versions: often toned down, conventionalized, elevated literary language
- **relativity** of aesthetic value: variants embedded in the work's **dynamic structure**, i.e.: stylistic tendency as part of 'literary evolution' (new vs. old canon → Lessing's 'rules')

Jan Mukařovský: *Varianty a stylistika* (1930)

For the fundamental question [...] ([...] how stylistics can make use of the variants of poetic texts for its own purposes), it follows [...] that the analysis of variants is, for stylistics, an effective means of searching for the **structural principles** that determine a poet's style. For in the improvements and alterations in the text these principles, active **tendencies** that indicate the **direction** of the improvements, find much clearer expression than in the finished, completed work, where they exist in a latent and static state.

Miroslav Červenka: Textologie und Semiotik (1970) in *Texte und Varianten*

- shift of focus: from multitude of single variants to one change of the work's structural unity
- layers relevant as origin of variation vs. layers relevant for holistic criticism
- variants as selection from a potential paradigm
- variant as 'sign' for
 - a. individual style (during composition)
 - b. elimination of external / accidental influences on a work (in retrospect)
 - c. influence of later developments / works (in retrospect)
 - d. literary evolution (in retrospect; → Mukařovský)

Italian “variantistica”

Source: Paola Pugliatti: *Textual Perspectives in Italy ...* (1998)

- focus on revised **authorial** manuscripts (rich holograph tradition)
- study of variants as description of **regularities**
- influence of structuralism (C. Segre): text as evolving system (diachronic) across synchronic structures

Gaps

- methodological limits (from Lessing onwards):
human overview of variants → hypotheses / general observations about a subset of substantive variants → illustration with examples
(analyses always selective, i.e., incomplete, opaque)
- based on diachronic stages of synchronic systems (versions), i.e., not applicable to genetic variation (revision vs. writing process)
- lack of shared and explicit theoretical ground
- focus on interpretation → no descriptive framework

3. Which way forward in digital / AI age?

Fundamental alternatives

analysis of variants

- limited (controllable) steps: spot variants, then analyze them
- context: may be ignored—possibly relevant (e.g., punctuation)
- prerequisite: definition of classes (e.g., substantive vs. accidental)

holistic / global comparison

- complex (opaque) process: broader characterisation of textual “change”
- prerequisites:
 - units of comparison (chunking)
 - operationalisation of “change”
 - distance measures

Immediate first step: typological classification

Typology of variants

Accidentals	Substantives	Orthographical	Transposition	Substitution	Amplification
Contamination	Correction	Modification	Interpolation	Emendation	Intervention
Monolingual / Multilingual	Lacuna/damaged/gap / blank space	Internal/external	Typographic	Omission	Addition
Deletion	Graphical	Punctuation	Glyphs (and Diacritics)	Indel	Abbreviation

From: Lorentz Workshop “Seeing the Difference: Visualizing Textual Variation” (April 2025)

Aim

1. rule-based and LLM-based processing to separate (possibly) substantive variants from accidental ones
2. transformation into textual annotations

Approximation: variants in

- punctuation → (probably) accidental
- orthography → accidental
- apostrophization → (probably) accidental
- none of these → possibly substantive

Example corpus: Goethe's *Miscellaneous Poems* (1789)

Comparison of printed version (*Schriften*, S) to:

1. preceding autograph of the poem's collection (H³, H⁴, 1788)
numerous of (mostly minor) variants
2. early versions from the 'young Goethe' period (JG, 1769–75)
literary evolution from 'genius era' to classicism (→ Mukařovský)
numerous substantive variants (but also minor ones)

4. Experiments

Classification Pipeline

Variant Classification Types

Classification Results

Examples

- In {Dickigts Schauer|Dickichts-Schauer} → orthographic variant, punctuation variant
- Er {hett|hätt} kein Auge davon verwandt → orthographic variant
- Meine lieben Waisen nicht {ersehe|erblicke} → other (possibly substantive)
- Die {fröhlichsten| köstlichen} Stunden des {traurigen|eilenden} → other (possibly substantive)

Conclusion, open questions, future work

1. LLMs can help to analyse variants by classifying them beyond where purely rule-based approaches would fail.
2. Classification is not self-evident (not even for humans).
3. How to make classification context-sensitive? (substantive variation in punctuation, grammar)
4. Can LLMs offer valid and reliable holistic comparisons?